

CREATING MICE TOURISM DESTINATION BRAND IN SAMARKAND

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15117459>

Annotation: The article discusses importance of developing a strong brand identity for destinations targeting MICE (Meetings, Incentives, Conferences, and Exhibitions) tourism, significance of branding in attracting international business events and enhancing a destination's competitiveness. The author highlights essential elements such as infrastructure, accessibility, government support, and marketing strategies that contribute to a successful MICE brand. The study also examines case studies of well-established MICE destinations, providing insights into best practices and challenges in brand positioning.

Keywords: MICE tourism, business meetings, marketing, touristic image, infrastructure.

Introduction:

Nowadays, due to high profitability of MICE tourism, which has stimulated stiff competition between destinations. The MICE sector is an important contributor to destination image at regional and national levels. Including MICE activities, business travel has long been a focus of growth by public agencies and the tourism industry, because business travelers are known to be higher spenders than leisure travelers. MICE tourism is also desirable because it can extend the tourism season far beyond the traditional holiday peaks and tourism amenities can be expanded by developing exhibition and conference facilities. According to researches co-created MICE branding strategy can support complimentary sectors to benefit local residents and expand a destination's tourism portfolio. During times of crisis, innovation in the recovery phase is required to bring business tourism back.

Also, it is considered important to increase the attractiveness of the region for business women and to develop business tourism services, and in order to increase the flow of tourists in many countries, MICE tourism, that is, meetings, organizing various events, conferences and exhibitions for promotion, has been developed. In particular, Singapore is one of the most attractive countries in Southeast Asia that has become a center for conferences and events. In 2023, the income of MICE events in the country will reach 3.82 billion US dollars.

According to statistics, 1 out of 3 enterprises in developed countries are managed by women, while in low-income countries this indicator corresponds to 1 out of 4. This shows the influence of women on the income level of the country.

Organization of various events, exhibitions, conferences for women, and development of business tourism services, with the effective use of tourist resources of Samarkand region, will contribute to increasing the visit of business women tourists to the region. According to statistics, the number of MICE tourism facilities in Samarkand region was 5 in 2016, and now it has increased to 20. Research shows that business travelers spend four times more than non-business travelers. Therefore, business tourism has a positive effect not only on the country, but also on the economic income of local residents. Also, business tourism contributes to the development of tourism infrastructure, as well as to the development of other types of tourism, for example, cultural, pilgrimage or adventure tourism. At the same

time, it helps to spread the touristic image of the region. To increase the attractiveness of the business tourism image of the region, development of the following types of services is an important factor.

Figure 1. Important services for the development of MICE tourism in the region¹

First of all, the development of tourism infrastructure should provide facilities for holding various events and exhibitions. In this regard, the transport infrastructure is important, it is necessary to create free movement of tourists in the area, and convenience in terms of time. Another important factor is the quality of the internet connection. We know that in many developed countries, 5G networks and free Wi-Fi systems provide convenience for tourists. The speed and quality of Internet connection is especially important in various meeting, exhibition and event processes. Of course, in order to create a favorable image of the area for business forums, there should be special halls for exhibitions and meetings. Security is considered very important for business women and contributes to the development of the touristic image of the region. Also, in order to spend their free time effectively, a tourist destination should offer a lot of activities, tours, shopping or entertainment programs. We know that female travelers are very interested in the culinary culture of the country, therefore, the development of gastronomic tourism services in the region will contribute to the positive impression of female travelers who come to various events.

In our opinion, holding various fashion shows in the region and attracting experts in this field will not be of interest to any woman or girl. Holding fashion events not only increases the value of the host city, but also positively affects its competitiveness and tourist image, ensuring the flow of tourists. Also, holding fashion shows in the region during the summer and winter seasons ensures the balance between the seasonality of tourism in the region. Women who attend fashion shows bring family members with them and use other tourism services, including hotels, unique shopping, and pilgrimages, which benefit the industry. In general, the holding of fashion shows in the region not only contributes to economic growth, but also the exchange of cultural experiences, strengthening the relationship between tourists and destinations.

Conclusion:

The article concludes that creating a successful MICE tourism destination brand requires a multi-faceted approach integrating strong infrastructure, efficient marketing, and

¹ Muallif ishlanmasi

collaboration among stakeholders, including government bodies, event organizers, and the hospitality sector. It emphasizes the need for destinations to differentiate themselves by offering unique experiences, leveraging digital marketing, and ensuring sustainable practices. Ultimately, a well-defined brand identity strengthens a destination's global positioning, attracts high-profile events, and drives economic growth.

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